

ISic1646

I.Sicily inscription 1646

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. In N(omine) D(omi)ni I(e)h(s)u
2. XP(ist)j hoc
3. sepulc
4. rum anastas
5. i trapezitae
6. Χ(ριστός) Μ(αρίας) Γ(ενόμενος)

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494044

EDCS 12700075

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.84
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 203-205
Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I
e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.
Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 579 fig.11

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354714>